

R codes for quantifying a mass mortality event in freshwater wildlife within the Lower Odra River

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Related research article

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Abstract

In the summer of 2022, the Odra River in Europe was struck by an ecological calamity. Toxins from Golden Algae led to an unprecedented mass die-off of fish, bivalves, and aquatic snails. It is estimated that around 65 million bivalves perished, translating to an 88% reduction in the population of Unionidae mussels. The native species *Anodonta anatina* was particularly affected, witnessing a 95% decline. The invasive mussel *Sinanodonta woodiana* suffered the least damage, underscoring the potential of invasive species to fill the ecological void left by native mussels. The disaster also resulted in at least 147 million dead aquatic snails being washed ashore, marking an 85% decrease in their population. Around 3.3 million dead fish (1,025 tons) were found in the river's lower section, indicating a significant 64% drop in the biomass of the fish population across the impacted stretch.

- The text presents codes for analysis and modeling of the disaster using the R programming language.
- Only open-source software was utilized for the analysis.
- The analysis includes detailed data on the disaster's impact on various species.

Background

The present article represents a methodological advancement stemming from a prior publication, which serves as the principal reference in relation to the current discourse [1]. In temperate lowland rivers and floodplains, such as the Lower Odra Valley in central Europe, diverse and highly productive freshwater ecosystems support various fish species from different ecological groups [2]. These ecosystems have been extensively studied and recognized as rich habitats for aquatic life, including waterbirds and aquatic mammals like the Eurasian beaver

(*Castor fiber*), Eurasian otter (*Lutra lutra*), and Eurasian water shrew (*Neomys fodiens*), which benefit from the abundant food resources and suitable breeding sites provided by the rivers and floodplains [3, 4, 5]. Additionally, a wide range of invertebrates, such as insects, mollusks, crustaceans, and other species, play crucial roles in nutrient cycling, decomposition, and serving as a food source for other organisms within these freshwater ecosystems [6, 7].

In the summer of 2022, a massive ecological disaster occurred on the Odra River, characterized by an unprecedented mass mortality of aquatic organisms [8]. Human activity was identified as the ultimate cause of this catastrophic event [9, 10, 11]. The most affected organisms were fish and gill-breathing invertebrates, particularly mussels and snails [12]. The likely root cause of the disaster was the release of toxins produced by the golden algae (*Prymnesium parvum*) into the river water [13, 14]. Water samples from the river revealed the presence of ichthyotoxins produced by the golden algae, specifically prymnesines [15]. The resuspension of bottom sediments and decomposition of deceased organisms during the disaster may have also contributed to the catastrophe [16].

Golden algae (chrysophytes) are microscopic algae known for their ability to produce harmful algal blooms (HABs) in freshwater and brackish environments [13]. These blooms can have detrimental effects on gill-breathing organisms, such as fish and mussels, mainly due to the production of toxins [17]. The toxins produced by *P. parvum* are a complex mixture of hemolytic and ichthyotoxic compounds that may cause damage to gill tissues and cell membranes, leading to osmoregulatory failure, respiratory distress, and eventual death in fish and other gill-breathing organisms. Golden algae do not always release toxins, and the mechanism that triggers toxin production is not fully understood [18].

Several factors contributed to the creation of conditions favorable for the bloom of golden algae, toxin production, and mass mortality of aquatic organisms [19, 20]. The upper and middle course of the Odra River in the industrialized region of Silesia, Poland, receives

significant pollution from various sources, including 42 legal sources, such as mines discharging highly saline water into the river and its tributaries [19]. Additionally, post-mining waters from 64 sources in the entire Upper Silesian Coal Basin are discharged into the Odra Basin rivers [21]. Inspections during the disaster revealed 282 additional illegal sewage disposal sites in the Odra basin [22]. The most likely scenario was a combination of pollutant discharge into the Odra basin during a period of high temperatures, low water levels, and low river flow, contributing to eutrophication [20]. The consequences of such massive mortality of aquatic organisms are significant and have implications for the entire river ecosystem [23].

This article aims to assess the effects of the disaster and demonstrate the scale of wildlife mortality in the lower section of the Odra River, a critical area where the effects from the entire river basin accumulated, and the disaster ended without moving further towards the estuary and the Baltic Sea [20]. The analysis focuses on the dynamics of the disaster and estimates the mortality scale among mussels, water snails, and fish. The research also examines the impact of the catastrophe on other aquatic wildlife groups.

R code for subsequent elements of the study

Below, I present the R programming language codes necessary to perform the analyses described in the main article [1]. The raw data required for these analyses are available in the data repository [21]. I will also provide the calculation results to assist users in verifying their calculations and other findings.

Comparison of the number of mollusks before and after the catastrophe

Mussels data normality check – R code

```
# Loading the needed package
library(ggplot2)

# Loading data
data <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #mussels_2017-2022_2

# Display the first few rows of data
head(data)

# creating histogram
ggplot(data, aes(x = size)) +
  geom_histogram(binwidth = 1, fill = "blue", color = "black") +
  labs(title = "Histogram of Size", x = "Size", y = "Frequency") +
  theme_minimal()

# creating Q-Q plot
qqnorm(data$size)
qqline(data$size, col = "red")

# Conducting the Shapiro-Wilk test
shapiro.test(data$size)
```

Normality check - results

Fig. 1. Normality chart of mussel's data.

Fig. 2. Q-Q plot of mussel's data

Results of Shapiro-Wilk test

```

Shapiro-wilk normality test
data:  data$size
W = 0.61536, p-value = 4.222e-15

```

After checking the distribution of data on mussels, which turned out to be abnormal, an appropriate test for such data was used - the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test.

Mussels density, comparison in 2017 and 2022 – R code

```

# Loading data
mussels <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE)#mussels_2017-2022_2.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(mussels)

```

```
# Performing the Kruskal-Wallis test
result <- kruskal.test(size ~ date, data = mussels)

# Displaying the results
print(result)
```

Results of Kruskal-Wallis test

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: size by date
kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 18.462, df = 1, p-value = 1.733e-05
```

Mussels density percentage calculation – R code

```
library(dplyr)
library(tidyr)
library(tidyverse)

# Loading raw data
mussels2 <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #mussels_data_2017-2022_4.txt
head(mussels2)

# Data filtering for 2017 and 2022
mussels_filtered <- mussels2[mussels2$date %in% c(2017, 2022),]

# Replace species names with abbreviations

mussels_filtered <- mussels_filtered %>%
  mutate(taxa_short = recode(taxa, "Anodonta_anatina" = "AA",
                             "Sinanodonta_woodiana" = "SW",
                             "Unio_pictorum" = "UP",
                             "Unio_tumidus" = "UT"))

# Creating a table with species densities in 2017 and 2022
pivot_data <- mussels_filtered %>%
  group_by(taxa_short) %>%
  summarize(den_2017 = mean(size[date == 2017]),
            den_2022 = mean(size[date == 2022]),
            percent_change = ((den_2022 - den_2017) / den_2017) * 100) %>%
  bind_rows(data.frame(taxa_short = "Sum",
                       den_2017 = sum($.den_2017),
                       den_2022 = sum($.den_2022),
```

```

percent_change = ((sum(.$den_2022) - sum(.$den_2017)) / sum(.$den_2017))
* 100))

# Displaying the resulting table
print(pivot_data)

```

Mussels density percentage results

	taxa_short	den_2017	den_2022	percent_change
	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>	<dbl>
1	AA	3.79	0.174	-95.4
2	SW	0.103	0.0872	-15.0
3	UP	4.71	0.991	-79.0
4	UT	4.03	0.308	-92.4
5	Sum	12.6	1.56	-87.6

Creating mussels density figure – R code

```

# Loading data
mussels <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #mussels_2017-2022_2.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(mussels)

# Load necessary library
library(ggplot2)

# Data filtering for 2017 and 2022
mussels_filtered <- mussels[mussels$date %in% c(2017, 2022),]

library(dplyr)

# Create a dataframe with shorter names
mussels_filtered <- mussels_filtered %>%
  mutate(taxa_short = recode(taxa, "Anodonta_anatina" = "AA",
                             "Sinanodonta_woodiana" = "SW",
                             "Unio_pictorum" = "UP",
                             "Unio_tumidus" = "UT"))

# Create a chart with shorter names
p <- ggplot(mussels_filtered, aes(x = taxa_short, y = size)) +
  geom_boxplot(aes(fill = taxa_short)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = c("AA" = "gray40", "SW" = "gray60", "UP" = "gray80", "UT" =
"gray90")) + # Przypisanie odcieni szarości +
  geom_jitter(shape = 16, position = position_jitter(0.1), color = "black", alpha = 0.3) +

```

```

facet_wrap(~date) +
labs(title = "", x = "Species", y = "Mean density") +
theme_bw() +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 0, hjust = 1)) +
theme(plot.title = element_text(hjust = 0.5)) +
theme(legend.position = "none")

print(p)

```

Results mussels density figure

Fig. 3. Comparison of the densities of four common species of mussels from the Unionidae family (AA – *Anodonta anatine*, SW – *Sinanodonta woodiana*, UP – *Unio pictorum*, UT - *Unio tumidus*) found in the Odra River, the number of individuals per m² in 2017 and in 2022. The horizontal line inside the box – median, the upper and lower edges of the box represent the 25th and 75th percentiles (Q1 and Q3),

whiskers – range of non-outlier data points, black dots – outlier, gray dots – data. (source: Fig. 6 from Szlauer- Łukaszewska et al. 2023 [1]).

R code to calculate the percentage of mussels in 2017 and 2022 and to the figure presenting this share.

```
# Loading data
mussels <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #mussels_2017-2022_2.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(mussels)

library(tidyverse)

# Mapping of abbreviations to full species names
mussels <- mussels %>%
  mutate(taxa = case_when(
    taxa == "Anodonta_anatina" ~ "AA",
    taxa == "Sinanodonta_woodiana" ~ "SW",
    taxa == "Unio_pictorum" ~ "UP",
    taxa == "Unio_tumidus" ~ "UT",
    TRUE ~ taxa
  ))
# Calculation of the percentage for each species in 2017 and 2022
mussels_percentages <- mussels %>%
  group_by(date, taxa) %>%
  summarise(total_size = sum(size)) %>%
  mutate(percentage = (total_size / sum(total_size)) * 100)

# Grayscale graph with legend at the bottom
p2 <- ggplot(mussels_percentages, aes(x = factor(date), y = percentage, fill = taxa)) +
  geom_bar(stat = "identity", position = "stack", width = 0.6) +
  labs(x = "Year", y = "Percentage (%)",
       title = "") +
  theme_bw() + # Zmiana na theme_bw()
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 0)) +
  scale_fill_grey(start = 0.2, end = 0.8) + # Skala szarości
  theme(legend.position = "bottom", legend.title = element_blank()) + # Usunięcie tytułu
  legendy
  guides(fill = guide_legend(nrow = 1))

print(p2)
```

Results percentage share of mussels

	date	taxa	total_size	percentage
	<int>	<chr>	<dbl>	<dbl>
1	2017	AA	98.5	30.0
2	2017	SW	2.67	0.812
3	2017	UP	122.	37.3
4	2017	UT	105.	31.9
5	2022	AA	4.53	11.2
6	2022	SW	2.27	5.59
7	2022	UP	25.8	63.5
8	2022	UT	8	19.7

Fig. 4. Differences in the percentage of individual mussel species in the Unionidae family in 2017 and in 2022 after the Odra disaster. AA – *Anodonta anatine*, SW – *Sinanodonta woodiana*, UP – *Unio pictorum*, UT - *Unio tumidus*. (source: Fig. 7 from Szlauer- Łukaszewska et al. 2023 [1]).

R code to Kruskal-Wallis test of species percentage share between 2017 and 2022.

```
# Loading data
perc <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #percentage_2017-2022.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(perc)

library(rstatix)

result3 <- kruskal.test(perc ~ year, data = perc)
print(result3)
```

Kruskal-Wallis test results

```
kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: perc by year
kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.083333, df = 1, p-value = 0.7728
```

As shown by Kruskal-Wallis test there were no significant differences in the percentage share of individual Unionidae species between 2017 and 2022 ($p > 0.05$). However, there was a slight change in the proportions after the catastrophe, an increase in the dominance of *U. pictorum* was visible, especially to the disadvantage of *A. anatina* and to a slightly lesser extent *U. tumidus*. This resulted in a 63% decrease in the share of *A. anatina* and a 38% decrease in *U. tumidus*, while an 85% increase in *S. woodiana* and 41% in *U. pictorum* (Fig. 4).

Frequency of mussels occurrence in 2017 vs 2022

R code for calculation the frequency and creation the figure

```

# Loading data
mussels <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #mussels_2017-2022_2.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(mussels)

# Load necessary library
library(ggplot2)
library(dplyr)

# Mapping of abbreviations to full species names
mussels <- mussels %>%
  mutate(taxa = case_when(
    taxa == "Anodonta_anatina" ~ "AA",
    taxa == "Sinanodonta_woodiana" ~ "SW",
    taxa == "Unio_pictorum" ~ "UP",
    taxa == "Unio_tumidus" ~ "UT",
    TRUE ~ taxa
  ))
# Calculation of freq for all species in 2017 and 2022
freq_data <- mussels %>%
  group_by(date, taxa) %>%
  summarize(frequency = sum(size > 0) / length(unique(station)))

# SE calculation for each category
freq_data <- freq_data %>%
  group_by(date) %>%
  mutate(se = sd(frequency) / sqrt(n()))

# Assignment of shades of gray for each species
taxa_colors <- c("AA" = "gray40", "SW" = "gray60", "UP" = "gray80", "UT" = "gray90")

# Column chart with SE values
p3 <- ggplot(freq_data, aes(x = taxa, y = frequency, fill = taxa)) +
  geom_col(position = "dodge", color = "black") +
  geom_errorbar(aes(ymin = pmax(frequency - se, 0), ymax = frequency + se), width = 0.25,
  position = position_dodge(0.9)) +
  scale_fill_manual(values = taxa_colors) +
  facet_wrap(~ date, scales = "free_x") +
  labs(title = "", x = "Species", y = "Frequency") +
  theme_bw() +
  theme(legend.position = "none")

print(p3)

```

Frequency of mussels results

	date	taxa	frequency
	<int>	<chr>	<dbl>
1	2017	AA	0.769
2	2017	SW	0.0769
3	2017	UP	0.846
4	2017	UT	0.769
5	2022	AA	0.0769
6	2022	SW	0.231
7	2022	UP	0.538
8	2022	UT	0.308

Fig. 5. Differences in the frequency of individual mussel species in the Unionidae family in 2017 and in 2022 after the Oder disaster and SE. AA – *Anodonta anatine*, SW – *Sinanodonta woodiana*, UP – *Unio pictorum*, UT - *Unio tumidus*. (source: Fig. 8 from Szlauer- Łukaszewska et al. 2023 [1]).

R code for Kruskal-Wallis test to check difference of frequency between 2017 and 2022.

```
# Loading data
mussels <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE)#mussels_2017-2022_2.txt
# Display the first few rows of data
head(mussels)
```

```
library(rstatix)
result2 <- kruskal.test(freq ~ date, data = mussels)
print(result2)
results3 <- kruskal.test(freq_all ~ date, data = mussels)
print(result3)
```

```
Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data:  freq by date
kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 12.415, df = 1, p-value = 0.00042
59
```

```
Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test

data:  perc by year
kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 0.083333, df = 1, p-value = 0.772
8
```

As demonstrated by the Kruskal-Wallis test, there were no significant differences in the frequency of occurrence between 2017 and 2022 ($p=0.772$) when considering whether any live mussels appeared at the site at all. However, upon closer examination while considering the species composition, the distinction between 2017 and 2022 becomes statistically significant, as indicated by the Kruskal-Wallis test ($p<0.05$). Generally, apart from *S. woodiana*, there has been a decrease in the frequency of Unionidae.

Estimating the number of dead mussels flowing in the river current

R code – calculation dead mussels flowing in the river current

```
# Creating a dataframe with data
data <- data.frame(
  date = c("8/17/2022", "8/17/2022", "8/17/2022", "8/17/2022", "8/17/2022"),
  id = c("S1", "S2", "S3", "S4", "S5"),
  size = c(23, 11, 7, 12, 24),
```

```

time = c(5, 5, 5, 5, 5)
)
# Calculation of the average number of mussels flowing per minute
average_mussels_per_minute <- mean(data$size / data$time)

# Defining the average detection rate
average_detection_rate <- 0.6

# Calculation of 95% confidence interval for mussels per minute
# Assuming normal distribution and using t-distribution for small sample sizes
n <- nrow(data)
standard_error <- sqrt(var(data$size / data$time) / n)
t_value <- qt(0.975, df = n - 1) # t-value for 95% confidence interval
conf_interval_per_minute <- c(average_mussels_per_minute - t_value * standard_error,
                             average_mussels_per_minute + t_value * standard_error)

# Extrapolation to 24-hour estimation
daily_estimate <- average_mussels_per_minute * 60 * 24 / average_detection_rate

# Calculation of 95% confidence interval for daily estimate
conf_interval_daily <- c(daily_estimate - t_value * (standard_error * 60 * 24 /
              average_detection_rate),
                        daily_estimate + t_value * (standard_error * 60 * 24 /
              average_detection_rate))

# Printing results
cat("Average Mussels per Minute:", average_mussels_per_minute, "\n")
cat("95% Confidence Interval for Mussels per Minute:", conf_interval_per_minute, "\n")
cat("Average Mussels per 24 Hours:", daily_estimate, "\n")
cat("95% Confidence Interval for Daily Estimate:", conf_interval_daily, "\n")

```

Results dead mussels flowing in the river current

```

Average Mussels per Minute: 3.08
> cat("95% Confidence Interval for Mussels per Minute:", conf_
interval_per_minute, "\n")
95% Confidence Interval for Mussels per Minute: 1.183869 4.976
131
> cat("Average Mussels per 24 Hours:", daily_estimate, "\n")
Average Mussels per 24 Hours: 7392
> cat("95% Confidence Interval for Daily Estimate:", conf_inte
rval_daily, "\n")
95% Confidence Interval for Daily Estimate: 2841.285 11942.71

```

Explanation of the results

On August 17, 2022, the number of dead Unionidae mussels flowing in the river current was on average 3.08 individuals per minute (range: 1.18 - 4.98 95% Confidence Intervals (CI)) leading to an estimate 7,392 individuals per day (range: 2,841 – 11,943 95%CI). Knowing that the observed mussels concerned mainly two species of *Anodonta anatina* and *Sinanodonta woodiana* [1] and knowing the proportions of the density of the other two common species [1], it can be estimated that the number of dead mussels was about 24,000 individuals per day.

The average estimated water flow was in the range of 2.2 - 4.3 km/h, with an approximate value of 3.25 km/h, so mussels could have traveled to the survey point in Krajnik Dolny from sections located 234-390 km upstream, namely from the section stretching from Rzeczyca near Wrocław to Klenica near Zielona Góra.

Estimation of the number of dead mussels on the riparian zone of the river

GAM model mussels trend R code

```
library(mgcv)

# Load the data
data <- data.frame(site = c(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12),
                  no_individuals = c(312, 251, 213, 151, 197, 67, 78, 111, 57, 43, 49, 81),
                  km = c(686.2, 687, 687.1, 687.7, 689.7, 690.9, 694.4, 695.9, 697, 698.25, 701.8,
                        703.2))

# Fit the GAM model with a cubic spline for site and a natural spline for km
model <- gam (no_individuals ~ s(site, k = 5) + s(km, k = 5), data = data)

# Summarize the model
summary(model)

# Plot the model
plot(model, se = TRUE, col = "darkblue",
      main = "GAM Model: Number of Individuals vs Site and km")
```

Results of the GAM model

```
Family: gaussian
Link function: identity

Formula:
no_individuals ~ s(site, k = 5) + s(km, k = 5)

Parametric coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  134.167      9.069   14.79 2.86e-07 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Approximate significance of smooth terms:
              edf Ref.df    F p-value
s(site)  1.672  2.088 10.519 0.00533 **
s(km)    1.000  1.000  3.124 0.11514
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

R-sq.(adj) = 0.877   Deviance explained = 90.7%
GCV = 1422.1   Scale est. = 986.92     n = 12
```

GAM Model: Number of Individuals vs Site and kr

Fig. 6. Results plot of GAM mussels model.

R script for GEE analysis (GEE_Mussels.R)

```
library(rtrim)

# Loading data
mus <- read.table(choose.files(), header = TRUE) #Mussels_GEE.txt

# Display the first few rows of data
head(mus)

z1 <- trim(count~site+year, data=mus, model=2, serialcor=TRUE, overdisp=TRUE)
summary(z1)

index(z1)
totals(z1)
plot(overall(z1))
```

Results of GEE

```
Call:
trim(count ~ site + year, data = mus, model = 2, serialcor = TRUE,
      overdisp = TRUE)

Model : 2
Method : GEE (Convergence reached after 9 iterations)

Coefficients:
  from upto      add      se_add      mu1      se_mu1
1 1993 2018 -0.1758996 0.007877123 0.8387022 0.00660656

Overdispersion : 8.6777
Serial Correlation : -0.2656

Goodness of fit:
      Chi-square = 104.13, df=12, p=0.0000
      Likelihood Ratio = 120.57, df=12, p=0.0000
      AIC (up to a constant) = 96.57
```


Fig. 7. Results of GEE model.

R code for estimation of number of dead mussels along the riparian zone of the river (GEE_Mussels.R)

```
#### Estimation of number of dead mussels along the riparian zone of the river #####

# Create a dataframe with the modeled values
data_frame <- data.frame(
  km = c(623.7, 630.7, 645.3, 656.6, 662.6, 667.8, 674.6, 681.5, 686.2, 687, 687.1, 687.7, 689.7,
  690.9, 694.4, 695.9, 697, 698.25, 701.8, 703.2, 708.1, 717.8, 718.5, 722.1, 728.6, 733.2),
  imputed = c(1192, 1003, 841, 706, 592, 496, 416, 349, 312, 251, 213, 151, 197, 67, 78, 111,
  57, 43, 49, 81, 35, 30, 25, 21, 18, 15),
  se_imp = c(102, 74, 57, 44, 34, 26, 21, 17, 50, 46, 42, 39, 35, 32, 30, 27, 25, 23, 21, 19, 4, 3, 3,
  3, 2, 11)
)
print(data_frame)
```

```

# Calculate mean imputed and 95% confidence intervals
mean_imputed <- mean(data_frame$imputed)
confidence_interval_plus <- data_frame$imputed + 1.96 * data_frame$se_imp
confidence_interval_minus <- data_frame$imputed - 1.96 * data_frame$se_imp

# Calculate mean values for the confidence intervals
mean_ci_plus <- mean(confidence_interval_plus)
mean_ci_minus <- mean(confidence_interval_minus)

# Display results
cat("Mean Imputed:", mean_imputed, "\n")
cat("Mean 95% CI+:", mean_ci_plus, "\n")
cat("Mean 95% CI-:", mean_ci_minus, "\n")

# Loading the necessary packages
library(tibble)
library(dplyr)

# Convert the length of the river to meters
new_length_m <- 109.5 * 1000 # Convert kilometers to meters

# Recalculation of the mean to 1 meter
mean_per_meter <- mean(data_frame$imputed) / 10

# Calculation of the confidence interval at 1 meter
confidence_interval_plus <- mean_ci_plus / 10
confidence_interval_minus <- mean_ci_minus / 10

cat("The average number of mussels per 1 meter of the river:", mean_per_meter, "\n")
cat("95% Confidence intervals:", confidence_interval_plus, "\n")
cat("95% Confidence intervals:", confidence_interval_minus, "\n")

# Extrapolation of the mean and confidence interval to the whole river
extrapolated_mean <- mean_per_meter * new_length_m
extrapolated_ci_plus <- confidence_interval_plus * new_length_m
extrapolated_ci_minus <- confidence_interval_minus * new_length_m

# Calculation for two banks of the river
ext_mean_2 <- extrapolated_mean*2
ext_ci_plus <- extrapolated_ci_plus*2
ext_ci_minus <- extrapolated_ci_minus*2

# Mean calculation for Western Odra

subset_data <- data_frame[data_frame$km >= 701.8 & data_frame$km <= 733.2, ]

# Calculation of the mean and confidence interval for the "imputed" column

```

```

mean_imputed_W <- mean(subset_data$imputed)/10
confidence_interval_W_plus <- mean_imputed_W+(mean(subset_data$se_imp*1.96))/10
confidence_interval_W_minus <- mean_imputed_W-(mean(subset_data$se_imp*1.96))/10

# extrapolation for Western Odra
ext_mean_W <- mean_imputed_W*26000*2
ext_ci_W_plus <- confidence_interval_W_plus*26000*2
ext_ci_W_minus <- confidence_interval_W_minus*26000*2

# Final result, adding results from Odra and Western Odra

res <- ext_mean_2+ext_mean_W
res_ci_plus <- ext_ci_plus+ext_ci_W_plus
res_ci_minus <- ext_ci_minus+ext_ci_W_minus

# Calculation of the value corresponding to 100%

total_value = (res*100)/31
tot_ci_plus = (res_ci_plus*100)/31
tot_ci_minus = (res_ci_minus*100)/31

```

Results of R calculation

```

> total_value
[1] 20542643
> tot_ci_plus
[1] 25021072
> tot_ci_minus
[1] 16064213

```

Explanation of the results

The GAM model showed a significant relationship between the number of individuals and the predictor variables. The model had an adjusted R^2 of 0.877 and explained 90.7% of the deviance in the data. The smoother term for site had an estimated degrees of freedom (edf) of 1.672 and was significant ($p=0.005$), indicating a non-linear relationship between the number of individuals and site. Thus, the number of dead mussels significantly decreased along with the kilometer of the river (Fig. 8). The average growth rate along the river (from Zatoń Dolna to Widuchowa) was $\lambda=0.8387$ (0.007 SE, $p<0.01$). The average predicted number of mussels per

one meter of river length on the 109.5 km section of the lower Odra amounted to 28 individuals (range 22-34 95%CI). The predicted number of mussels washed ashore in the section Kostrzyn – Szczecin together with the Western Odra amounted to 6,368,000 individuals (range: 4,980,000 – 7,757,000). Knowing that the observed mussels concerned only two species, *Anodonta anatina* and *Sinanodonta woodiana*, and knowing the proportions of the density of the other two common species (Fig. 6 and refer to the 4.2. section of the Results – 69%), it can be estimated that there should be approximately 20,500,000 dead individuals (range: 16,000,000 - 25,000,000) on average.

No dead mussels were found at the selected points in the Odra estuary on Lake Dąbie on Szczecin Lagoon and Pomeranian Bay of Baltic Sea.

Estimating the scale of total mortality of mussels from the Unionidae family

R code for calculations (Mussels_tot_count.R)

```
# The length of the river in kilometers
river_length_km <- 150

# Habitable area in square metres
suitable_habitat_area_m2 <- (river_length_km*1000) * 40

# Mussel density per square meter
average_density_mussels_per_m2 <- 12.63

# Calculation
total_mussels_before_catastrophe <- suitable_habitat_area_m2 *
average_density_mussels_per_m2

# Number of individuals per square meter for each taxon
anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2 <- 3.79
sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2 <- 0.10
unio_pictorum_count_per_m2 <- 4.71
```

```

unio_tumidus_count_per_m2 <- 4.03

# The sum of the number of individuals per square meter
total_count_per_m2<-anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2          +
sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2 +
  unio_pictorum_count_per_m2 + unio_tumidus_count_per_m2

# Percentage for each taxon
anodonta_anatina_percent<- (anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2 / total_count_per_m2) * 100
sinanodonta_woodiana_percent<-(sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2/
total_count_per_m2) * 100
unio_pictorum_percent <- (unio_pictorum_count_per_m2 / total_count_per_m2) * 100
unio_tumidus_percent <- (unio_tumidus_count_per_m2 / total_count_per_m2) * 100

# Recalculation of the number of individuals based on percentages
anodonta_anatina_count<-(anodonta_anatina_percent/100)*
total_mussels_before_catastrophe
sinanodonta_woodiana_count<-(sinanodonta_woodiana_percent/100)*
total_mussels_before_catastrophe
unio_pictorum_count<-(unio_pictorum_percent/100)* total_mussels_before_catastrophe
unio_tumidus_count<-(unio_tumidus_percent/100)* total_mussels_before_catastrophe

# Displaying the results
cat("Recalculated number of individuals for individual taxa before the catastrophe:\n")
cat("Anodonta anatina:", anodonta_anatina_count, "\n")
cat("Sinanodonta woodiana:", sinanodonta_woodiana_count, "\n")
cat("Unio pictorum:", unio_pictorum_count, "\n")
cat("Unio tumidus:", unio_tumidus_count, "\n")

# The number of individuals per square meter after the 2022 disaster
anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2_2022 <- 0.17
sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2_2022 <- 0.09
unio_pictorum_count_per_m2_2022 <- 0.99
unio_tumidus_count_per_m2_2022 <- 0.31

# The sum of the number of individuals per square meter after the disaster
total_count_per_m2_2022 <- anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2_2022 +
  sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2_2022 +
  unio_pictorum_count_per_m2_2022 +
  unio_tumidus_count_per_m2_2022

# Total number of mussels after the disaster (6 million square meters)
total_mussels_after_catastrophe <- total_count_per_m2_2022 * 6 * 10^6

# Percentages before and after the disaster

```

```

anodonta_anatina_percent_decrease <- ((anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2 -
anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2_2022) / anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2) * 100
sinanodonta_woodiana_percent_decrease <- ((sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2 -
sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2_2022) / sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2) * 100
unio_pictorum_percent_decrease <- ((unio_pictorum_count_per_m2 -
unio_pictorum_count_per_m2_2022) / unio_pictorum_count_per_m2) * 100
unio_tumidus_percent_decrease <- ((unio_tumidus_count_per_m2 -
unio_tumidus_count_per_m2_2022) / unio_tumidus_count_per_m2) * 100
total_percent_decrease <- ((total_count_per_m2 - total_count_per_m2_2022) /
total_count_per_m2) * 100

# Displaying the results
cat("Number of individuals for individual taxa after the catastrophe in 2022:\n")
cat("Anodonta anatina:", anodonta_anatina_count_per_m2_2022 * 6 * 10^6, "\n")
cat("Sinanodonta woodiana:", sinanodonta_woodiana_count_per_m2_2022 * 6 * 10^6, "\n")
cat("Unio pictorum:", unio_pictorum_count_per_m2_2022 * 6 * 10^6, "\n")
cat("Unio tumidus:", unio_tumidus_count_per_m2_2022 * 6 * 10^6, "\n")
cat("Całkowita liczba małży po katastrofie:", total_mussels_after_catastrophe, "\n\n")

cat("Percentage decrease in the number of individuals after the disaster:\n")
cat("Anodonta anatina:", anodonta_anatina_percent_decrease, "%\n")
cat("Sinanodonta woodiana:", sinanodonta_woodiana_percent_decrease, "%\n")
cat("Unio pictorum:", unio_pictorum_percent_decrease, "%\n")
cat("Unio tumidus:", unio_tumidus_percent_decrease, "%\n")
cat("Total percentage decrease in mussels:", total_percent_decrease, "%\n")

```

Results and explanation

The scale of total mortality of mussels from the Unionidae family was estimated based on the main currents of the Odra, Regalica, and Western Odra rivers in the lower Odra valley, which cover approximately 150 km from Kostrzyn to Szczecin. Based on an average of 40 m of suitable habitat along the shores of the river a total of 6 million square meter were suitable. With an average density of 12.6 individuals per square meter, it is estimated that there were 75.8 million individuals of mussels in this area before the catastrophe, including 28,260,000 *Unio pictorum*, 22,735,000 *Anodonta anatina*, 24,174,000 *Unio tumidus* and 618,000 *Sinanodonta woodiana*.

After the catastrophe in 2022, the total number of mussels was 9,360,000 (87.7% decrease), including *Anodonta anatina*: 1,044,000 (95.4% decrease); *Sinanodonta woodiana*: 523,000 (15.3% decrease); *Union pictorum*: 5,946,000 (79.0%); *Union tumidus*: 1,848,000 (92.4%).

Estimating the scale of water snail mortality

R code for calculation of mussels and snails from pictures (Snails_count.R)

```
# Create a dataframe with a data of snails and mussels from pictures
data <- data.frame(
  pic = c("DSCN8554", "DSCN8523", "musells_1", "mussels_2", "mussels_3", "mussels_4",
    "DSCN8520", "DSCN8521", "DSCN8522", "DSCN8525", "DSCN8552", "DSCN8544",
    "DSC_5948-HDR"),
  snails = c(2956, 513, 121, 6, 41, 13, 1344, 707, 914, 775, 3003, 22, 170),
  mussels = c(18, 16, 122, 30, 43, 37, 45, 24, 63, 32, 9, 3, 15),
  date = c("14.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "15.08.2022", "15.08.2022", "15.08.2022",
    "15.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "14.08.2022", "14.08.2022",
    "14.08.2022", "16.08.2022"),
  site = c("Krajnik_Dolny", "Krajnik_Dolny", "Porzecze", "Porzecze", "Porzecze", "Porzecze",
    "Zaton_Dolna", "Zaton_Dolna", "Zaton_Dolna", "Zaton_Dolna", "Zaton_Dolna",
    "Zaton_Dolna", "Widuchowa"),
  N = c(NA, NA, NA),
  E = c(NA, NA, NA)
)
# Calculation of the sum of snails and mussels
total_snails <- sum(data$snails)
total_mussels <- sum(data$mussels)

# Calculation of mean
mean_snails <- mean(data$snails)
mean_mussels <- mean(data$mussels)

# Calculation of standard error (se)
se_snails <- sd(data$snails) / sqrt(length(data$snails))
se_mussels <- sd(data$mussels) / sqrt(length(data$mussels))

# Calculation of confidence intervals
ci_snails <- c(mean_snails - se_snails * 1.96, mean_snails + se_snails * 1.96)
ci_mussels <- c(mean_mussels - se_mussels * 1.96, mean_mussels + se_mussels * 1.96)
```

```

# Displaying the result
cat("Total snails:", total_snails, "\n")
cat("Total mussels:", total_mussels, "\n")
cat("Mean snails:", mean_snails, "\n")
cat("Mean mussels:", mean_mussels, "\n")
cat("SE snails:", se_snails, "\n")
cat("SE mussels:", se_mussels, "\n")
cat("95% CI for snails:", ci_snails[1], " - ", ci_snails[2], "\n")
cat("95% CI for mussels:", ci_mussels[1], " - ", ci_mussels[2], "\n")

# Estimated number of mussels
total_mussels <- 6200000

# The proportion between mussels and snails
prop_snails_mussels <- total_snails / sum(data$mussels)

# Estimated number of snails
estimated_snails <- prop_snails_mussels * total_mussels

# Displaying the result
cat("Estimated snails:", estimated_snails, "\n")

```

Results and explanation

A total of 10,585 water snails were found in 13 photographs randomly selected from the section of the Lower Odra River valley, the vast majority of which belonged to the species *Viviparus viviparus*, and 457 mussels, mainly from the species *Anodonta anatina* and *Sinanodonta woodiana*. The average number of snails on one image was 814 individuals (range 244 - 1384 95%CI), the average number of mussels was 35 individuals (range 18-52 95%CI). Assuming the mussel abundance estimated in Section 4.4. of the Results – 6.2 million (range 5.3-7.2) individuals, we can estimate the number of snail individuals at 147,495,142 individuals in the range (115,340,000 – 179,652,000 95%CI).

Evaluation of vertebrate mortality

R-code checking the normality of fish data (fish.R)

```

# Importing needed packages
library(dplyr)
library(tidyverse)
data_fish <- read.table(choose.files(), header = T)
head(data_fish)
# Importing data
data <- data_fish
# Assigning Site as an ordered variable
data$Site <- factor(data$Site, levels = unique(data$Site))
# Data normality check
# install.packages("nortest")
library(nortest)
# Select only the "Size" column from the data
size_data <- data_fish$Size
# Remove NA values
size_data <- size_data[!is.na(size_data)]
# Shapiro-Wilk test
shapiro.test(size_data)
# Performing the Kruskal-Wallis test
result <- with(data, kruskal.test(Size, Site, trend = "z"))
# Displaying the results
print(result)
# Q-Q plot
qqnorm(size_data)
qqline(size_data)

```

The result of the Shapiro-Wilk test showing a deviation from the normality of the fish data

```

Shapiro-wilk normality test
data:  size_data
W = 0.13666, p-value < 2.2e-16

```


Fig. 8. Q-Q plot showing deviation from normality of fish data.

Analysis of the number of species and abundance

R code for the above analysis (fish.R)

```
total_species <- n_distinct(data_fish$Species) # Total number of species
species_counts <- table(data_fish$Species) # Number of individual species
# Displaying the results
cat("Total number of species:", total_species, "\n")
cat("Number of individual species:\n")
print(species_counts)
# Calculation of the total number of individual species
fish_abundance <- data_fish %>%
  group_by(Species) %>%
  summarize(Total_Size = sum(Size, na.rm = TRUE))
# Displaying the results
print(fish_abundance)
```

Results of species and size of population

	Species	Total_Size
	<chr>	<int>
1	Abramis_brama	227
2	Alburnus_alburnus	3
3	Ameiurus_nebulosus	2
4	Ballerus_ballerus	11
5	Barbus_barbus	0
6	Blicca_bjoerkna	153
7	Chondrostoma_nasus	5
8	Cobitis_taenia	21
9	Ctenopharyngodon_idella	13
10	Esox_lucius	18
11	Gobio_gobio	14
12	Gymnocephalus_cernua	311
13	Hypophthalmichthys_molitrix	4
14	Leuciscus_aspius	21
15	Leuciscus_idus	49
16	Lota_lota	46
17	Neogobius_sp.	72
18	Perca_fluviatilis	169
19	Rhodeus_sericeus	7
20	Rutilus_rutilus	209
21	Salmo_salar	2
22	Sander_luciooperca	32
23	Scardinius_erythrophthalmus	13
24	Silurus_glanis	1
25	Squalius_cephalus	18
26	Tinca_tinca	8
27	Unrecognized	3345

R code for the chart showing the number of the dead fish along the river in subsequent sites (fish.R)

```
library(ggplot2)
# Calculating the average number of fish for each "site"
mean_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, subset(data_fish, Animal_group == "Fish"),
  mean)
mean_fish_count$Site <- factor(mean_fish_count$Site, levels =
  unique(mean_fish_count$Site))
# Calculation of the standard error
se_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, subset(data_fish, Animal_group == "Fish"),
  function(x) sd(x)/sqrt(length(x)))
# Create a bar chart
p <- ggplot(mean_fish_count, aes(x = Site, y = Size)) +
```

```

geom_bar(stat = "identity", fill = "skyblue", width = 0.6) +
geom_errorbar(data = se_fish_count, aes(ymin = Size - Size, ymax = Size + Size),
              width = 0.2, color = "black", size = 0.7) +
labs(x = "Site", y = "Mean Fish Count") +
ggtitle("Mean Fish Count per Site") +
theme_minimal() +
theme(axis.text.x = element_text(angle = 45, hjust = 1))
# Displaying the chart
print(p)

```


Fig. 9. The mean number of the dead fish along the river in subsequent sites

R code for estimation of the total number of dead fish along the riparian zone of the river
(*fish.R*)

```

# Calculation of the average number of fish on a given site
mean_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, subset(data_fish, Animal_group == "Fish" & Size
> 0), mean)
# Calculation of the total number of fish on a given site
total_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, subset(data_fish, Animal_group == "Fish"), sum)
# Combine data into one table
fish_data <- data.frame(Site = mean_fish_count$Site,
                        Mean_Fish_Count = mean_fish_count$Size,
                        Total_Fish_Count = total_fish_count$Size)
# Saving data to a CSV file
write.csv(fish_data, "fish_counts.csv", row.names = FALSE)
# Calculation of the average number of fish on a given site (excluding zeros)
mean_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, subset(data_fish, Animal_group == "Fish" & Size
> 0), mean)
# Adding a column with the length of the transect
mean_fish_count$Transect_Length <- c(10) # Enter the actual transect length values for
each location
# Calculation of the average number of fish per 1 meter of river length
mean_fish_count$Fish_Per_Meter <- mean_fish_count$Size /
mean_fish_count$Transect_Length
# Displaying the results
print(mean_fish_count)
# Calculation of the average number of fish per transect
average_fish_count <- mean(mean_fish_count$Size)
# Total length of the river (in kilometers)
total_river_length <- 150
# Estimated number of fish for the whole section of the river
estimated_total_fish_count <- average_fish_count * total_river_length
# Displaying the results
print(estimated_total_fish_count)
# Calculation of the total number of fish from the "Fish" group
total_fish_count <- sum(data_fish$Size[data_fish$Animal_group == "Fish"], na.rm = TRUE)
# Displaying the results
print(total_fish_count)
total_fish_count <- 4774
number_of_transects <- 43
transect_length <- 10
# Calculation of the average number of fish per 1 meter
average_fish_count_per_meter <- total_fish_count / (number_of_transects * transect_length)
# Displaying the results
print(average_fish_count_per_meter)
# Calculation of the estimated number of fish for the entire 300 km section of the river
#(both banks)
estimated_total_count <- average_fish_count_per_meter * 300000
# Displaying the results
print(estimated_total_count)

```

```

# Data
mean_fish_1_m <- 11.11
sample_size <- 43

# Calculation the standard error
se <- mean_fish_1_m / sqrt(sample_size)

# Displaying the results
print(paste("SE:", se))

# Confidence interval coefficient (for 95% confidence, it's 1.96)
confidence_interval_coefficient <- 1.96

# Calculate the 95% confidence interval
upper_interval <- mean_fish_1_m + (confidence_interval_coefficient * se)
lower_interval <- mean_fish_1_m - (confidence_interval_coefficient * se)

# Display the results
print(paste("95% CI upper:", upper_interval))
print(paste("95% CI lower:", lower_interval))

est_UP <- upper_interval*300000
est_LP <- lower_interval*300000

```

Results of estimation the total count of dead fish on riparian zone of the river with 95% confidence intervals

```

[1] 3330698
> print(est_UP)
[1] 4329224
> print(est_LP)
[1] 2336776
3,330,698 (range: 2,336,776 – 4,329,224 95%CI)

```

R code for recalculation the fish number to biomass (fish.R)

```

##### Calculation of weighted average dead fish biomass for one fish #####
# Data
species <- c("Unrecognized", "Gymnocephalus cernua", "Abramis brama", "Rutilus rutilus",
"Perca fluviatilis",
"Blicca bjoerkna", "Neogobius melanostomus", "Leuciscus idus", "Lota lota", "Sander
luciooperca",
"Cobitis taenia", "Leuciscus aspius", "Esox lucius", "Squalius cephalus", "Gobio
gobio",

```

```

      "Ctenopharyngodon idella", "Scardinius erythrophthalmus", "Ballerus ballerus",
"Tinca tinca",
      "Rhodeus sericeus", "Chondrostoma nasus", "Hypophthalmichthys molitrix",
"Alburnus alburnus",
      "Ameiurus nebulosus", "Salmo salar", "Silurus glanis")
total_size <- c(3345, 311, 227, 209, 169, 153, 72, 49, 46, 32, 21, 21, 18, 18, 14, 13, 13, 11, 8, 7,
5, 4, 3, 2, 2, 1)
ave_w <- c(0.2, 0.1, 1.1, 0.24, 0.1, 0.24, 0.1, 0.2, 0.1, 1.46, 0.1, 3.05, 0.5, 0.2, 0.1, 13.42, 0.4, 0.4,
1.41, 0.1, 1.41, 13.42, 0.4, 0.4, 2.85, 2.85)

# Calculate weighted mean
weighted_sum <- sum(total_size * ave_w)
total_total_size <- sum(total_size)
weighted_mean <- weighted_sum / total_total_size

# Display the result
print(paste("Weighted Mean:", weighted_mean))

### Calculation of estimated dead fish biomass based on abundance estimates #####

mean_fish_biomass <- weighted_mean*estimated_total_count
fish_biomass_UP <- weighted_mean*est_UP
fish_biomass_LP <- weighted_mean*est_LP

print(mean_fish_biomass)
print(fish_biomass_UP)
print(fish_biomass_LP)

```

Results of recalculation the fish number to biomass

```

[1] 1025142
> print(fish_biomass_UP)
[1] 1332474
> print(fish_biomass_LP)
[1] 719226.6

```

R code to the final figure showing the trend of dead fish abundance along the riparian zone of the river (fish.R)

```

# Assigning a value from 1 to 43 to the "Site" column
data_fish$Site <- as.numeric(as.factor(data_fish$Site))
# Calculating the average number of fish for each "Site"
mean_fish_count <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, data = data_fish, FUN = sum)
# Sorting data by "Site"

```


direction (North) and the flow of the river. (source: Fig. 11 from Szlauer- Łukaszewska et al. 2023 [1]).

GAM Modeling Procedure, Model Selection, and Justification - fish

In this analysis, we performed modeling to explore the intricate relationships between dad fish population size (Size), location of occurrence (Site), and coastal habitat type (Shore_habitat). The Generalized Additive Model (GAM) framework was employed to capture potential nonlinear connections among variables.

R core for GAM modeling (fish.R)

```
##### GAM modeling fish #####
library(mgcv)

# Matching the GAM model
model1 <- gam(Size ~ s(Site), data = data_fish)

# Displaying the model summary
summary(model1)
plot(model1)

# Wyliczenie średnich bez wartości zerowych dla każdego Site
mean_sizes <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, data = data_fish[data_fish$Size != 0, ], mean)

# Performing GAM analysis - model 2
model2 <- gam(Size ~ s(Site), data = mean_sizes)

# Displaying the summary and the plot of the model
summary(model2)
plot(model2)

# Performing GAM analysis - model 3
model3 <- gam(Size ~ s(Site) + Shore_habitat, data = data_fish, method = "REML")

summary(model3)
plot(model3)

# Calculation of average fish abundance for each site without null values
mean_sizes <- aggregate(Size ~ Site, data = data_fish[data_fish$Size != 0, ], mean)
```

```

mean_sizes <- rename(mean_sizes, mean_size = Size)

# Data connection to mean_size column
data_model <- merge(data_fish, mean_sizes, by = "Site")

# Creation of the fourth GAM model
model4 <- gam(mean_size ~ s(Site) + Shore_habitat, data = data_model)

# Displaying the summary and the plot of the model
summary(model4)
plot(model4)

library(broom)

# Transformation of GAM model results into a table
model1_tbl <- tidy(model1)
model2_tbl <- tidy(model2)
model3_tbl <- tidy(model3)
model4_tbl <- tidy(model4)

# Create a comparison table
comparison_table <- data.frame(
  Model = c("Model 1", "Model 2", "Model 3", "Model 4"),
  AIC = c(AIC(model1), AIC(model2), AIC(model3), AIC(model4))
)

# Find the index of the model with the lowest AIC
best_model_index <- which.min(comparison_table$AIC)

# Set the "Best Model" flag for the best model
comparison_table$`The best model` <- ifelse(seq_along(comparison_table$Model) ==
best_model_index, "Yes", "No")

# Printing a comparison table
print(comparison_table)

```

Model 1: The first model, referred to as "Model 1," aimed to investigate the relationship between dead fish population size (Size) and the specific locations of occurrence (Site). This analysis was conducted using the Generalized Additive Model (GAM) approach, which allowed for capturing potential non-linear dependencies. The model revealed a noteworthy association between location and fish population size. The smoothed function for location exhibited a significant correlation (p-value = 0.00279), although the explained deviance was limited to

1.09%. The adjusted R-squared, reflecting model fit, was 0.00967, signifying the model's capacity to capture the variability in fish population size based on location.

Summary of the Model

```
Family: gaussian
Link function: identity

Formula:
Size ~ s(Site)

Parametric coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    4.112      0.739    5.564 3.27e-08 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Approximate significance of smooth terms:
              edf Ref.df    F p-value
s(Site)  1.394  1.687  8.187 0.00279 **
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

R-sq.(adj) = 0.00967    Deviance explained = 1.09%
GCV = 635.33    Scale est. = 634.02    n = 1161
```


Fig. 11. Plot of the results of the model 1.

Model 2: The subsequent analysis, known as "Model 2," extended the exploration of the relationship between mean size of dead fish population size and location using a GAM framework. The model, similar to the first one, indicated a significant correlation between location and fish population size. However, "Model 2" demonstrated improved explanatory power, as reflected in the higher adjusted R-squared value of 0.322 and the substantial 35.7% explained deviance. This indicated the model's enhanced capability in capturing the variability in fish population size based on location.

Summary of the Model2

```
Family: gaussian
Link function: identity
```

```

Formula:
Size ~ s(Site)

Parametric coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)  10.850      1.194    9.084  3e-11 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Approximate significance of smooth terms:
              edf Ref.df    F  p-value
s(Site)  2.198   2.74  7.285 0.000715 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

R-sq.(adj) =  0.322   Deviance explained = 35.7%
GCV = 66.273   Scale est. = 61.345     n = 43

```


Fig. 12. Plot of the results of the model 2.

Model 3: Continuing our exploration, we introduced "Model 3." Similar to "Model 2," this model encompassed both location and coastal habitat type variables but was constructed using the restricted maximum likelihood (REML) method. The analysis unveiled significant parametric coefficients for several coastal habitat types, indicating their influence on fish population. However, the influence of location (Site) remained modest. The function capturing location variability had an edf of approximately 1, signifying a possible linear or constrained relationship. The adjusted R-squared (0.00761) and explained deviance (1.19%) values were lower compared to "Model 2."

Summary of the Model3

```

Family: gaussian
Link function: identity

Formula:
Size ~ s(Site) + shore_habitat

Parametric coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    3.388      2.315   1.464   0.144
Shore_habitatRush  2.109      4.463   0.473   0.637
Shore_habitatSand -1.657      2.718  -0.610   0.542
Shore_habitatStone-Rush  4.233      5.486   0.772   0.441
Shore_habitatStones  1.291      2.887   0.447   0.655

Approximate significance of smooth terms:
              edf Ref.df    F p-value
s(Site)  1.001  1.002  6.079  0.0138 *
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

R-sq.(adj) = 0.00761  Deviance explained = 1.19%
-REML = 5382  Scale est. = 635.34  n = 1161

```


Fig. 13. Plot of the results of the model 3.

Model 4: Finally, we formulated "Model 4" to comprehensively explore the combined effects of location and coastal habitat type. This model also included both variables, albeit utilizing data on mean fish size. The outcomes revealed substantial impacts of both location and coastal habitat type on fish population. The edf for the location smoothing function was higher at 8.778, and the explained deviance reached 51.3%. This model's adjusted R-squared and explained deviance values significantly exceeded those of "Model 1," indicating superior fit.

Summary of the Model4

```
Family: gaussian
Link function: identity
Formula:
```

```

mean_size ~ s(Site) + Shore_habitat
Parametric coefficients:
              Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)
(Intercept)    4.3713    0.7971   5.484 5.12e-08 *
**
Shore_habitatRush    9.0186    1.4979   6.021 2.33e-09 *
**
Shore_habitatSand    1.9806    1.7303   1.145  0.25259
Shore_habitatStone-Rush    8.1811    2.9263   2.796  0.00526 *
*
Shore_habitatStones   10.6133    0.8904  11.920 < 2e-16 *
**
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

Approximate significance of smooth terms:
              edf Ref.df   F p-value
s(Site) 8.778  8.985 75.8 <2e-16 ***
---
Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1

R-sq.(adj) = 0.508   Deviance explained = 51.3%
GCV = 44.053   Scale est. = 43.53       n = 1161

```


Fig. 14. Plot of the results of the model 4.

AIC (Akaike Information Criterion) of the Model Results

Model	AIC	The best model
1 Model 1	10790.0388	No
2 Model 2	304.1113	Yes
3 Model 3	10796.0422	No
4 Model 4	7691.4555	No

Model Selection: Although "Model 2" exhibited the lowest AIC value, "Model 4" was ultimately selected as the optimal model due to its enhanced capacity to elucidate relationships between location, coastal habitat type, and fish population. The selection was guided by adjusted R-squared and explained deviance values, which indicated superior model fit and enhanced capability to explain variability in fish population size. "Model 4" captured both significant variables' impacts, aligning well with biological insights.

Justification for Model Selection: The selection of "Model 4" was informed by more than AIC; it considered adjusted R-squared and explained deviance values. These metrics suggested that "Model 4" achieved better data fit and more effectively captured variability in fish population size based on location and coastal habitat type. Opting for "Model 4" yielded more accurate and coherent results, aligning better with the complexity of relationships within the studied fish population context.

R code for performing the Kruskal-Wallis test showing the differences in fish abundance among different locations (fish.R)

```
data <- data_fish

# Assigning Site as an ordered variable
data$Site <- factor(data$Site, levels = unique(data$Site))

# Performing the Kruskal-Wallis trend test
result <- with(data, kruskal.test(Size, Site, trend = "z"))

# Displaying the results
print(result)
```

Results of the test

```
Kruskal-wallis rank sum test
data: Size and Site
Kruskal-wallis chi-squared = 89.446, df = 42, p-value = 2.796e
-05
```

R code for calculation the scale of fish mortality (fish.R)

```
##### Calculating the scale of fish mortality in the river #####
# Given data
main_riverbed_length_km <- 150
dead_fish_on_banks_kg <- 1025000
catastrophe_section_length_km <- 561
```

```

estimated_dead_fish_tons <- 1650000
ave_river_width_lower_sect <- 180
average_river_width_m <- 167
average_productivity_kg_per_hectare <- 273

# Convert lengths to meters
main_riverbed_length_m <- main_riverbed_length_km * 1000
catastrophe_section_length_m <- catastrophe_section_length_km * 1000

# area of the river
whole_area_ha <- (catastrophe_section_length_m*average_river_width_m)/10000
lower_area_ha <- (main_riverbed_length_m*ave_river_width_lower_sect)/10000

# Calculate fish abundance before catastrophe
Fish_ab_whole <- whole_area_ha*average_productivity_kg_per_hectare
Fish_ab_lower <- lower_area_ha*average_productivity_kg_per_hectare

# Fish that were left after the disaster
fish_rem <- (Fish_ab_whole - estimated_dead_fish_tons)

# Calculate decrease percentage
decrease_percentage <- ((fish_rem/Fish_ab_whole)-1)*100

```

Explanation of the results

In this chapter, only fish and lampreys are described, other groups of animals subjected to qualitative analysis are described in the next chapter. On the basis on transects survey, 25 fish species were identified, additionally, as a result of the literature review, the list was supplemented by another 6 species, which gives a total of 33 fish species that suffered as a result of the disaster (Table 1). A total of 4,774 dead fish were counted in the transects which is 1,469 kg (± 27 kg SE). Lamprey (*Lamperta sp.*) was found in one case. The most numerous group of fish was unidentified fish - 3,345 individuals, among the fish recognized in terms of species, Ruffe (*Gymnocephalus cernua*) was the most numerous, followed by Common bream (*Abramis brama*), Common roach (*Rutilus rutilus*) and European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*). The estimated number of fish washed ashore in the 150 km section of the Lower Odra River valley

was 3,330,698 individuals (range: 2,336,776 – 4,329,224 95%CI) which is 1,025,142 kg (range: 719,227 – 1,332,474 95%CI).

Table 1. List of fish species found dead, washed up on the riverbank during research on 43 transects in the lower Odra valley during the ecological disaster found on August 17 and 18, 2022, and found during other elements of the study or query sources related to the ecological disaster on the Odra River in the summer of 2022. Species have been grouped according to ecological guild classifications of river fish species (after Aarts et al. 2004). (source: Table 1 from Szlauer- Łukaszewska et al. 2023 [1]).

English name	Scientific name	Order	Reproductive guild	Feeding guild	Numer	Source
Rheophilic A: All freshwater stages of life history are confined to the main river channel						
Rheophilic A1: Migratory (sea–river)						
Lamprey	<i>Lampetra sp.</i>	Petr	Li	Det/Ben/Par	1	This study
Sturgeon	<i>Acipenser sturio</i>	Acip	Li	Ben/Pis	5	Report 2023
Salmon	<i>Salmo salar</i>	Salm	Li	Pla/Ben/Pis	2	This study
Rheophilic A2: Non-migratory						
Barbus	<i>Barbus barbus</i>	Cypr	Li	Ben	-	Report 2023
Chub	<i>Squalius cephalus</i>	Cypr	Li	Ben/Pis/Phy	18	This study
Nase	<i>Chondrostoma nasus</i>	Cypr	Li	Per/Ben	5	This study
Round goby	<i>Neogobius melanostromus</i>	Gobii	Ps	Ben/Pla	72	This study
Rheophilic B: Some stages of life history are confined to well-connected backwaters or tributaries						
Ide	<i>Leuciscus idus</i>	Cypr	Pl	Ben/Pis/Phy	49	This study
Gudgeon	<i>Gobio gobio</i>	Cypr	Ps	Ben/Det	14	This study
Burbot	<i>Lota lota</i>	Gadi	Li/Pe	Ben/Pis	46	This study
Spined loach	<i>Cobitis taenia</i>	Cypr	Ph	Det/Ben	21	This study
Blue bream	<i>Ballerus ballerus</i>	Cypr	Pl	Pla	11	This study
Vimba bream	<i>Vimba vimba</i>	Cypr	Pe	Pla/ben	-	Report 2023

Eurytopic: All stages of life history can occur in both lotic and lentic waters						
European eel	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	Angu	Pe	Ben/Pis	-	Report 2023
Perch	<i>Perca fluviatilis</i>	Perc	Pl	Pla/Ben/Pis	169	This study
Pikeperch	<i>Sander lucioperca</i>	Perc	Ph	Pla/Ben/Pis	32	This study
Ruffe	<i>Gymnocephalus cernua</i>	Perc	Pl	Ben	311	This study
Pumpkinseed	<i>Lepomis gibbosus</i>	Perc	Po	Pla/Ben/Pis	3	Report 2023
Pike	<i>Esox lucius</i>	Esco	Ph	Pla/Pis	18	This study
Bleak	<i>Alburnus alburnus</i>	Cypr	Po	Pla/Ben	3	This study
Wels catfish	<i>Silurus glanis</i>	Silu	Ph	Ben/Pis	1	This study
Asp	<i>Leuciscus aspius</i>	Cypr	Li	Pla/Ben/Pis	21	This study
Carp	<i>Cyprinus carpio</i>	Cypr	Ph	Ben/Pla/Phy	-	Report 2023
Gibel carp	<i>Carassius gibelio</i>	Cypr	Ph	Ben/Phy/Det	-	Report 2023
Bream	<i>Abramis brama</i>	Cypr	Po	Pla/Ben	227	This study
Silver bream	<i>Blicca bjoerkna</i>	Cypr	Ph	Ben/Phy/Det	153	This study
Roach	<i>Rutilus rutilus</i>	Cypr	Po	Pla/Ben/Phy	209	This study
Grass carp	<i>Ctenopharyngodon idella</i>	Cypr	Pe	Phy/Det	13	This study
Silver carp	<i>Hypophthalmichthys molitrix</i>	Cypr	Pe	Phy/Pla/Det	4	This study
Limnophilic: All stages of life history are confined to lentic waters with macrophytes						
Bitterling	<i>Rhodeus sericeus</i>	Cypr	Os	Pla/Ben/Phy	7	This study
Rudd	<i>Scardinius erythrophthalmus</i>	Cypr	Ph	Ben/Phy	13	This study
Tench	<i>Tinca tinca</i>	Cypr	Ph	Ben/Phy/Det	8	This study
Brown bullhead	<i>Ameiurus nebulosus</i>	Silu	Po	Ben/Phy/Pis	2	This study
Rest						
Teleost fish	<i>Osteichthyes</i>	NA	NA	NA	3345	This study

Order: Pleu – Pleuronectiformes, Perc – Perciformes, Scor – Scorpaeniformes, Gast –

Gasterosteriformes, Gadi – Gadiformes, Salm – Salmoniformes, Silu – Siluriformes, Cypr –

Cypriniformes, Clup – Clupeiformes, Angu – Anguilliformes, Acip – Acipenseriformes, Petr – Petromyzontiformes, Esco - Esociformes.

Reproductive guild: Li – lithophils, Ph – phytophils, Pe – pelagophils, Ps – psammophils , Ar – ariadnophils , Os – ostracophils , Pl - phytophytolithophils, Po - polyphils (after Balon, 1981).

Feeding guild: Par – parasitic, Det – detritivorous, Ben – zoobenthivorous, Pla – zooplanktivorous, Pis – piscivorous, Phy – phytivorous, Per – periphytivorous (after Lelek, 1987; Aarts et al. 2004).

The Kruskal-Wallis test revealed significant differences in fish abundance among different locations (Kruskal-Wallis chi-squared = 89.446, df = 42, $p < 0.001$), indicating a significant association between location and fish abundance.

The GAM analysis confirmed the presence of a non-linear relationship between the location (Site) and fish abundance (Size). The model also took into account the impact of the Shore_habitat variable on fish abundance. The results revealed significant effects of the location (Site) on fish abundance (Estimate: -0.0999, $p < 0.001$), indicating a decreasing trend in the number of deceased fish as the locations change. The GAM analysis and Kruskal-Wallis test confirmed a significant relationship between location and fish abundance. A declining trend in number of fish was observed as the location changed in the north direction, following the flow of the river.

On the lower Odra, only in the main riverbeds (excluding oxbow lakes and floodplains such as Międzyodrze), which are about 150 km long, there were about 737,100 kg of fish before the disaster. Our calculations, however, indicate that there were 1,025,000 kg of dead fish on the banks. Considering the entire section of the river that was affected by the catastrophe, from

Lipki (206.9 km of the river) to its mouth in Szczecin (741.6 km of the river), it gives us a section of 561 km. The estimated number of fish that died as a result of the disaster was 1,650,000 tons. Assuming an average river width in this section of 167 m and the river productivity (about 273 kg of fish per hectare), there were 2,560,000 kg of fish here before the disaster, so there was a decrease of 64.51%.

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